

Determining the determinants of emerging selection and orientation according to expert opinions.

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Abstract

The Object of the study aims to determine the determinants of selection and orientation in the light of the opinions of football experts to build and design a model in the future for an objective evaluation on a scientific basis codified in the process of selection and orientation for football players. In this study, the researcher used the descriptive approach in the survey method for its relevance to the nature of the research. And to verify the objectives of this study, the researcher used a questionnaire containing a set of preparations for six basic determinants in the form of axes that came in succession, physical, motor determinants, skill determinants, morphological determinants, physiological determinants, psychological determinants and mental determinants. After judging a sample of 42 professors and experts from all over the country and abroad, and after the statistical treatment used, the results showed that the selection and orientation of juniors to practise football is based on determinants that are comprehensive for a set of preparations and capabilities for the requirements of football.

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1. Introduction

Because the game of football has received an increasing importance in various developed and developing countries, nowadays soccer is the most practiced sport in the world and a market in the billions (louzada, 2015). And it is the first sport in terms of practice and follow-up, more than 3 billion and 500 million people followed the world cup in Russia (FIFA, 2018). It is played by more than 265 million active players worldwide (FIFA, 2006) football is nowadays a practice in the world and a market move in billions. Therefore, the club able to recruit talented players and develop them to the maximum It may bring many advantages and economic benefits to the clubs. (louzada, 2015) It made researchers always think about finding the best scientific methods that work on developing the game and selecting talented people with high abilities and raising their levels in all the elements necessary to reach high levels and achieve the best results. It became clear that the high level can only be achieved by developing the basic conditions What any game needs from childhood “and not all sports disciplines have the same physical requirements” (ben chehida, 2018, p. 11). Players reach the highest levels in the most types of sports usually during the years from eighteen to twenty, and this requires them to train and compete ranging from Between eight to ten years. Therefore, it was important to select talented young people between the ages of eight or nine, before they start their growth spurt (Merslab, 2020, p. 193).

Sports selection is not considered a new phenomenon, used by the Eastern bloc countries since the early sixties and during the seventies, and achieved amazing results during the Olympic Games in 1972-1976-1980. This success is attributed to the application of the talent discovery. Australia was the first Western country to implement selection programs in 1994, and at the end of the 1990s, the Australian Amended Program was applied in other sports federations, such as Britain, which implemented the idea of a modified Australian program. (Abu Al-Ali Abdel-Fattah, 2016, p. 431) the process of selecting beginner athletes is an economic process that saves effort, and achieves the best results and brings the best sports elements in terms of physical, technical, psychological, physiological, social and educational, which helps in achieving the desired results.

The unscientific self-selection may lose the game unique technical abilities. While the use of the scientific method in the selection of talents ensures that,

the best talented elements reach the highest levels. Where a previous study by (Ben goua , 2004) indicated the absence of scientific indicators that trainers rely on in the selection process, using the random and subjective method through observation, which is considered insufficient.

In recent years, it has required scientific attention to the processes of selecting talented people so that they can be taken care of through the scientific programs that are prepared for that. Hoping to reach the highest sporting levels in the game. This has led to the conduct of many scientific researches in the field of determining selection criteria and priorities and the extent to which it is possible to predict the level that young people can achieve in the future according of those criteria. (Merslab, 2020, p. 193)

The process of selection and orientation is one of the most important processes that most sports teams go through in order to choose the best elements who have the ingredients for success and some qualifications that help them excel in this sport. (Beboucha, 2021)

“Talent Orientation” is related to talent detection and aims at motivating youngsters to choose a sport that matches the individual talent characteristics to one or more specific sport(s). (Papic, 2009).

Identification of talent for field games at an age is a complex matter in team sports (louzada, 2015). The selection is usually from a wide base and a large number of players. For example, Paradou Club selected 41 members out of 62,000 children from all over Algeria in the year 2000. (Bensalem, 2009)

Moreover, as for every sporting activity there are requirements (physical, technical, tactical, morphology, mental and psychological). The talented player is the one who possesses an integration of these requirements to help him reach high levels, until the youth reaches those high levels, he must have several factors and determinants, as “ there are determinants if they are available in the youngsters with certain degrees, it is possible to predict what can be he achieved”. The determinants of selection mean “a set of factors or abilities that must be available to the young person in order to provide the coach with an opportunity to predict him to achieve high sports levels in the future.” The goal and directing the player to the activity or competition that suits his capabilities and this contributes to providing a good model for selection and classification of youngsters in the future.” (Radwan Hassan Allawi, 2002, page 27)

To build a real sports base for sporting high levels of sport in any of the countries, where it is noticed that the advanced countries in sport have built their progress on ambitious plans based on sports selection.

This is what most of the previous studies concluded, but the failures of the young national teams continue, the last of which is the fall of the under-18 team in the Mediterranean Games in Oran 2022 and the inability to Pass the first round.

In light of the findings of previous studies, which agreed on the Algerian football's lack of strategy, planning and scientific foundations in selection and direction in the field of football and the use of self-observation and not relying on standardized tests (beboucha, 2018)(Samaha , 2018)

In order to select objectively based on scientific foundations, it is necessary to rely on determinants of selection and guidance Riyadh (chachou, 2019) (haouar, 2015)

The determinants of sports selection and guidance for youth less than 13 and 11 years old were addressed from the point of view of experts in football and some actors in the field of training and selection in the field of football. In order to help solve this problem, we must answer the general question of the study:

What are the determinants of sports selection and Orientation for youth under 13 years of age in football from the point of view of experts?

2. Method and Materials

Type of research follows the approach adopted by (Ahmed, 2019, page 26), and for this we used the descriptive approach using the survey method.

2.1. Participants

The research sample consisted of doctors and experts in sports training and football from different cities of the country and even from abroad from various Arab and international universities.

2.2. Materials

In this study, we relied on the questionnaire, which is defined as a set of compound questions in a systematic way on a specific topic, and then placed in a form that is sent to the concerned persons, and this is to obtain the answers contained in it. Each axis includes a set of preparations and capabilities, and the five-point Likert scale was adopted in order to extract

the degree of importance of preparations and capabilities in order to rely on them in selecting and guiding talented youth from the point of view of experts and specialists.

2.3. Design and Procedure

The research form includes six axes and 35 football preparations and abilities, which can be used by relevant experts and doctors to provide feedback on whether these preparations and abilities are suitable for age groups and rank them according to their importance. The method of calculating internal consistency is to use the same total score as that of expert sampling to express the internal consistency of correlation coefficient.

2.4. Statistical Analysis

spss 26 - Cronbach's Alpha -Standard deviation- Mean .Std Deviation.

3. Results

The research form consisted of six axes and 35 football preparations and abilities directed to experts and specialist doctors to benefit us in order to express their opinion about these preparations and abilities and their suitability for the age group and their arrangement according to their degree of importance. For the sample directed to the experts.

Table (01): shows the correlation coefficient of the expressions of the first axis (the physical aspect) and the total degree of the same axis for the sample of experts.

	capabilities and preparations	Item-Total Statistics				Reliability Statistics
		Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted	Cronbach's Alpha
1	Reaction speed	34.90	22.100	-,003	0,869	0,831
2	Running speed	33.20	23.289	-,143	0,858	
3	The explosive power of the lower extremities	33.40	19.822	,407	0,826	
4	The explosive power of the upper extremities	35.50	17.389	,888	0,784	
5	speed power	35.40	16.267	,862	0,779	
6	endurance performance	35.60	16.489	,895	0,777	
7	bearing speed	35.50	15.167	,917	0,768	
8	Flexibility	32.90	21.878	,293	0,833	
9	Neuromuscular Compatibility	33.20	331	,319	0,831	
10	Agility	32.90	22.544	,067	0,841	
11	balance	35.50	15.167	,917	0,768	

Through table (1) related to the axis of the physical and motor aspect it was distinguished by internal consistency. Where the results of the correlation coefficient ranged between 0,768 (endurance of speed) and 0.869 (running speed) that was greater than 0.60 at the significance level of 0.05. And this shows that there is consistency of statements with the degree the totality of the axis to which it belongs, which confirms the suitability of the axis on the sample of the research.

Table (02): shows the correlation coefficient of the expressions of the first axis (the skills aspect) and the total degree of the same axis for the sample of experts

	capabilities and preparations	Item-Total Statistics				Reliability Statistics
		Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted	Cronbach's Alpha
1	juggling	27,60	11,822	0,463	0,803	0,816
2	agility with ball	27,60	13,600	-0,035	0,848	
3	To dribble the ball	27,80	10,844	0,521	0,796	
4	short pass	27,60	11,822	0,463	0,803	
5	long pass	29,80	9,733	0,625	0,783	
6	Headed ball hit	30,10	11,211	0,579	0,791	
7	ball control	27,30	12,678	0,424	0,811	
8	tossing the ball force	29,90	8,322	0,824	0,748	
9	Shooting accuracy	29,90	9,878	0,801	0,758	

Through table No (2) which is related to the skill aspect axis, it was characterized by internal consistency. Where the results of the correlation coefficient ranged between 0.748 (tossing the ball force) and 0,848 (agility with ball) which is greater than 0.60 at the significance level of 0.05. And this is what shows that there is consistency of the statements with the total score of the axis to which it belongs, which confirms the suitability of the axis on the research sample.

Table (03): shows the correlation coefficient of the expressions of the first axis (the morphological aspect) and the total degree of the same axis for the sample of experts

	capabilities and preparations	Item-Total Statistics				Reliability Statistics
		Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted	Cronbach's Alpha
1	total body length	7,00	2,444	,842	,518	0,747
2	agility with ball	6,90	2,322	,640	,632	
3	To dribble the ball	7,10	2,100	,855	,476	
4	short pass	6,90	4,544	-,061	,910	

Through table (3) related to the axis of the morphological aspect, it was distinguished by internal consistency. where the results of the correlation coefficient ranged between 0.476 (Relationship between height and weight) and 0.910 (body fat percentage) which is greater than 0.60 at the significance level of 0.05. And this shows that there is consistency the phrases with the total degree of the axis to which it belongs, which confirms the suitability of the axis on the sample of the research.

Table (04): shows the correlation coefficient of the fourth axis (physiological aspect) with the total score of the same axis for the sample of experts.

	capabilities and preparations	Item-Total Statistics				Reliability Statistics
		Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted	Cronbach's Alpha
1	Vo2 max	4,40	0,933	,818	,333	0,747
2	pma	4,40	1,822	,307	,902	
3	vma	4,60	,933	,686	,524	

Through table No. (4) Related to the axis of the physiological aspect was characterized by internal consistency. Where the results the correlation coefficient ranges between 0.333 (Vo2 max) and 0.902 (pma) is greater than 0.60 at the significance level of 0.05 and this indicates that there is consistency of the statements with the total degree of the axis to which it belongs, which confirms the suitability of the axis on the sample of the research.

Table (05): shows the correlation coefficient of the fifth axis (the psychological aspect) with the total score of the same axis for the sample of experts.

	capabilities and preparations	Item-Total Statistics				Reliability Statistics
		Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted	Cronbach's Alpha
1	self-control	4,60	2,267	0,897	0,824	<u>0,910</u>
2	perseverance	4,50	2,056	0,735	0,951	
3	Mental toughness	4,70	2,011	0,854	0,840	

Through table (5) related to the axis of the morphological aspect, it was distinguished by internal consistency. Where the results of the correlation coefficient ranged between 0.476 (Relationship between height and weight) and 0.910 (body fat percentage) which is greater than 0.60 at the significance level of 0.05. And this shows that there is consistency the phrases with the total degree of the axis to which it belongs, which confirms the suitability of the axis on the sample of the research.

Table (06): shows the correlation coefficient of the fifth axis (the mental aspect) with the total score of the same axis for the sample of experts.

	capabilities and preparations	Item-Total Statistics				Reliability Statistics
		Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted	Cronbach's Alpha
1	Attention	5,50	,944	0,686	0,659	<u>0,790</u>
2	concentration	5,70	1,122	0,564	0,792	
3	perception	5,80	1,289	0,689	0,690	

Through table No. (6), which is related to the axis of the mental aspect, it is distinguished by internal consistency. Where the results of the correlation coefficient range between 0.659 (attention) and 0.792 (concentration) are greater than 0.60 at the significance level of 0.05, and this shows that there

is consistency of statements with the total degree of the axis to which it belongs, which confirms the appropriateness of the axis on the sample of the research.

Presentation and discussion of the results of the questionnaire directed to professors and expert doctors:

	N	Abilities	Standard deviation	Mean	The degree of importance	Likert Scale Response
	01	Reaction speed	0,594	2,48	2	Slightly Important
	02	Running speed	0,547	4,57	5	Very Important
	03	The explosive power of the lower extremities	0,544	4,60	5	Very Important
	04	The explosive power of the upper extremities	0,630	2,57	3	Moderately Important
	05	speed power	0,627	2,40	2	Slightly Important
	06	endurance performance	0,833	2,19	2	Slightly Important
	07	bearing speed	0,794	2,17	2	Slightly Important
	08	Flexibility	0,485	4,64	5	Very Important
	09	Neuromuscular Compatibility	0,701	4,40	4	Important
	10	Agility	0,501	4,57	5	Very Important
	11	balance	0,824	2,17	2	Slightly Important
	12	juggling	0,701	4,40	5	Very Important
	13	agility with ball	0,547	4,57	5	Very Important
	14	To dribble the ball	0,544	4,60	5	Very Important
	15	short pass	0,701	4,40	4	Important
	16	long pass	0,627	2,40	2	Slightly Important
	17	Headed ball hit	0,582	1,95	2	Slightly Important
	18	ball control	0,485	4,64	5	Very Important
	19	tossing the ball force	0,683	2,17	2	Slightly Important
	20	Shooting accuracy	0,547	2,43	2	Slightly Important
	21	total body length	0,633	2,55	3	Moderately Important
	22	Weight	0,665	2,40	2	Slightly Important
	23	Relationship between height and weight	0,821	2,24	2	Slightly Important
	24	body fat percentage	0,707	2,50	3	Moderately Important
	25	Vo2 max	0,633	2,55	3	Moderately Important
	26	pma	0,665	2,40	2	Slightly Important
	27	vma	0,821	2,24	2	Slightly Important
	28	self-control	0,550	2,45	2	Slightly Important
	29	perseverance	0,593	2,45	2	Slightly Important
	30	Mental toughness	0,705	2,12	2	Slightly Important
	31	Attention	0,552	2,50	2	Slightly Important
	32	concentration	0,547	2,45	2	Slightly Important
	33	perception	0,565	2,21	2	Slightly Important

Through Table (7) which is an analysis of the questionnaires addressed to professors and doctors, experts in football and sports training, we reached a set of abilities, physical and skill to select and direct talented athletes from the youth in football for the age group under 13 years and 11 years. The following abilities were (running speed - explosive power of the lower extremities - flexibility - agility - to dribble the ball - agility with the ball -

running with the ball - control of the ball) to a very important degree. As for what was very important, the abilities and preparations were as follows (neuromuscular coordination- short pass). As for the rest of the abilities and preparations, they ranged from an important degree to a small degree. As for it is very important to a small degree, we did not record any ability or preparation.

Training, we reached a set of abilities, physical and skill to selecting and directing talented young football players for the age group under 13 years and 11 years. The following abilities were (running speed - explosive power of the lower extremities - flexibility - agility - ball control - agility with the ball - running with the ball - control of the ball) to a very important degree. As for what was very important, the abilities and preparations were as follows (neuromuscular coordination- short pass). As for the rest of the capabilities and preparations, they ranged from an important degree to a small degree .As for it is very important to a small degree, we did not record any ability or willingness in it.

4. Discussion

With regard to the physical and kinetic determinants in the process of selecting and guiding talented young people. And through the results of Table n: (7) we notice that there are four abilities that most experts agreed upon as being very important and represented in flexibility whose arithmetic average was estimated at 4.64, corresponding to a degree of 5 on the scale Likert and with a standard deviation of 0.485 was estimated. Running speed as its arithmetic mean was estimated at 4.60, which corresponds to the fifth degree on the scale of importance according to the Likert scale. And with a standard deviation estimated at 0.547 this age stage is considered one of the largest periods in which the speed increases. (Abu Al-Ali Abdel-Fattah, 2016, p. 446) According to Mohamed Nasr El-Din Radwan, speed (moving speed) is a basic requirement for all playing centers (Muhammad Nasr Al-Din, 2017, p. 261). And agility with a mean of 4.57 and a standard deviation of 0.501, as (Mufti Ibrahim) believes that football requires speed in changing directions and the player's transition from one movement to another with or without the ball. Sprint speed showed the highest discrimination potential for predicting whom the football club ultimately

selected into their junior academy. (Fortin-Guichard, 2022) Economy of the effort required to accomplish motor performance. (Mufti Ibrahim, 2013, p. 13) .This characteristic, which is one of the requirements of football, as the player's control over his body and changing his directions every time with and without the ball is very important (dellal, 2008) and for the explosive power of the lower extremities, the mean was estimated at 4.60 and the standard deviation at 0.544. It is considered a basic requirement for players in different playing positions, and it is an ineffective factor for the upper limbs (Muhammad Nasr Al-Din, 2017, p. 261). As for the abilities that were extracted to a significant degree, they are neuromuscular compatibility with an arithmetic mean of 4.40 and a standard deviation of 0.701. Compatibility is the most important gateway for the athlete to enter with the group of talented players, because an individual who does not possess compatibility cannot achieve any great success in the sports field. (Muhammad Nasr Al-Din, 2017, p. 88).

In a significant degree, the explosive force ability of the upper extremities was with a mean of 2.57 and a standard deviation of 0.630. As for a significant degree, the reaction speed, speed characteristic, endurance performance, endurance came to an important degree. The means: (2.48 2.40 2.19 2.17) and standard deviations were estimated at (0.594 0.627 0.833 0.794), but to a very small degree, we did not record any ability or readiness. The results of the study agreed with both, (Fortin-Guichard, 2022) and (Beboucha, 2021). The soccer players classified as talented by expert coaches have better physical skills than untalented ones.

As for the skill determinants, we notice that there are four preparations and abilities that most experts agreed on as being very important, which corresponds to a score of 5 on the likert scale. And it was represented in controlling the ball that its mean was estimated at 4.40, with a standard deviation of 0.701. Then agility with the ball where it's mean was estimated at 4.57 and with a standard deviation of 0.547 and running with a ball with a mean of 4.60 and a standard deviation of 0.544, then controlling the ball with a mean of 4.64 and a standard deviation of 0.485. As for the abilities that were extracted to a significant degree, which corresponds to the degree of 4 on the scale of the card, it's one ability represented in the short pass with an arithmetic mean of 4.40 and a standard deviation of 0.701. Either to a significant degree, we did not extract any ability with 0.630, or to a small degree important, (long passing, hitting the ball with the head, throwing the

ball, shooting accuracy), which average means: (2.40 1.95 2.17 2.43).
(0.627 0.582 0.683 0.547).

Conclusion

The subject of selection and guidance remains one of the important topics that require standing at it because of its importance and is considered the cornerstone of training in the sports field in general and in football in particular. And this can only be done by objective tests and measurements (ben goua, 2004). And to stay away from subjectivity and randomness as well as the use of modern means and technology where it is the only way to overcome the obstacles of selection and direction in Algerian football in order to advance in it and achieve the desired results and not waste other football talents. And this can only be done with scientific and correct foundations and standards.

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